

2.B: Hemodynamics

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Hemodynamics of an implanted pressure sensor in porcine and human pulmonary artery

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To assess whether in-silico models can be used to predict the risk of thrombus formation in pulmonary artery pressure sensors (PAPS), an in-silico study enhanced porcine animal study with 10 pigs. These sensors are implanted into the pulmonary artery aiming to detect earlier acute decompensation that can ideally be mitigated by pharmaceutical treatment of heart failure patients. 20 PAPS (one in a left and one in a right PA of each subject) were virtually implanted mimicking real implantations in pigs as acquired by CT in frames of an animal trial. First, we investigated hemodynamics by using CFD and assessed changes caused by PAPS. Transient flow simulations were done using STARCCM+. Since porcine and human PA differs, we investigated next the ability to translate these results onto human PA. PAPS were virtually implanted in human PA and CFD analysis of the hemodynamic changes due to PAPS implantation was done and results were compared with porcine results. Furthermore, we compared hemodynamics between optimally (sensors causing a minimal flow disturbance) and non-optimally (PAPS reaching from one vessel wall to the other, located within a side branch, or covering a side branch orifice) implanted sensors. Time-averaged wall shear stress (TAWSS), oscillating shear index (OSI) and pressure drop caused by a sensor were evaluated. We found a difference in hemodynamics between porcine and human PA resulting in lower TAWSS and higher OSI in human conditions that is associated with probably lower protection against risk of thrombus formation. PAPS implanted in the human PA causes relatively low averaged pressure drop of 0.84 ± 0.77 mmHg, which non-significantly differs from the pressure drop calculated in porcine PA with 0.70 ± 1.1 mmHg. Despite these differences in morphometry and hemodynamic parameters found in porcine and human PA, no higher risk of thrombus formation can be associated with a changed hemodynamics due to PAPS implantation. Despite the significantly lower TAWSS and significantly higher OSI found for PAPS in human PA both in silico studies (porcine and human) found no higher risk of thrombus formation for non-optimally implanted PAPS.

